

Nimble Artificial Intelligence driven robotic solutions for efficient and self-determined handling and assembly operations.

HORIZON-CL4-2022-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-04 - Intelligent work piece handling in a full production line

Grant Agreement n° 101091800

Project Coordinator: LMS

Consortium: STAM, TEK, IIT, RWTH, COMAU, CASP, TF-CC, UNIKIEV, CU, KLMN, DEC, AERNNOVA, CRIT, KIMM

D2.1: MASTERLY multi-disciplinary smart mechatronics - initial version

Deliverable nature	DEM - Demonstrator
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Contractual delivery date	30/06/2024
Actual delivery	29/06/2024
Version	V1
Lead Author	COMAU
Contributors	COMAU, IIT, LMS, TEK
Reviewer	IIT, LMS

Executive summary

The present deliverable provides an overview on the progress of the activities concerning the initial version of smart mechatronics devices. The deliverable is structured into six different sections, matching the task-architecture of Work Package (WP) 2. In particular, T2.1 and T2.2 are led by Comau and concern the development of AGVs and cooperating robots; T2.3 and T2.4 are led by IIT and describe the progress about the development of dexterous grippers to handle soft and rigid objects, respectively; while T2.5 and 2.6 are led by Tekniker and regard intelligent fixtures and smart cranes.

Table of contents

Executive summary	2
Table of contents	2
Table of figures	3
Table of tables	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Task-driven progress	7
2.1 Task 2.1: AGVs for storage, retrieval and conveying of parts.....	7
2.1.1 Hardware modules	9
2.2 Task 2.2: Cooperating robots	12
2.2.1 Hardware modules	12
2.2.2 Software modules	15
2.3 Task 2.3: Dexterous grippers for handling of flexible materials	16
2.3.1 Hardware modules	18
2.3.2 Software modules	20
2.4 Task 2.4: Grippers to handle rigid materials of variable size, shape and weight.....	21
2.4.1 Hardware modules	21
2.4.2 Software modules	23
2.5 Task 2.5: Intelligent stationary fixtures	30
2.5.1 Hardware modules	30
2.5.2 Software modules	35
2.6 Task 2.6: Smart cranes for autonomous transportation of large parts.....	36
2.6.1 Hardware modules	36
2.6.2 Software modules	39
3 Conclusions	43

Table of figures

Figure 1 - Schematic representation of the flexibility of the design the smart gripper, suitable for the three different pilot cases with the opportune tailored adjustments. The fingers of the gripper can move linearly (leftcolumn), rotate to grab large objects (central column), and spread open at 180 degrees to grab large flat surfaces (right column).	6
Figure 2 – Representation of the functional design of the smart gripper, including mechanical components and modelling the kinematics behaviour.....	7
Figure 3 - COMAU integrated mobile platform.....	8
Figure 4 - Schematic representation of the safety architecture scheme of the Agile1500.....	9
Figure 5 - COMAU Agile1500	9
Figure 6 - COMAU Agile1500 external dimensions	10
Figure 7 - Decathlon pilot case.....	12
Figure 8 - COMAU Racer5 Cobot	13
Figure 9 - COMAU Racer5 Cobot workspace section.....	13
Figure 10 - Schematic representation of the COMAU ROS driver architecture.....	15
Figure 11 - Representation of the conventional grippers tested at the Decathlon warehouse during the test sessions. The performance of a suction gripper was evaluated, by varying the number of suction caps, their width and the technology (i.e., vacuum or Venturi). Moreover, a two- and a three-finger grippers were tested.....	16
Figure 12 - A sample of the tests conducted at the Decathlon warehouse. Different grippers (by rows) are placed in position over the targetted product, once the grabs is secured, the products are lifted an manipulated to test the grasping stability and explore potential issues.	17
Figure 13 - A sample of the test products selected to evaluate the performance of conventional grasping strategies.....	17
Figure 14 - Representation of the selected linear actuators. Image downloaded from the manufacturer website.....	19
Figure 15 - Representation of the selected linear actuators. a) The slim model to install in the fingers. b) The bulky sensor to install in the palm of the gripper.....	19
Figure 16 - Representation of the final design of the first prototype of the gripper designed to meet the requirements of the Decathlon pilot case.	20
Figure 17 - Handling approach on complete pick and place operation.....	21
Figure 18 - Device mechanisms: 1) Lateral motion adjustment of suction cups, 2) Downwards motion of suction cups, 3) Rotation of suction cups, 4) Parallel clamp gripper.....	22

Figure 19 - Kinematics of mechatronic end-effector for small- to medium-sized components: a) downwards extension of suction cups, b) 90-degree rotation of suction cups, and c) Upwards retraction of suction cups, d) Parallel clamp. 23

Figure 20 - Velostat piezoresistive material configuration 24

Figure 21 - Tactile sensing configuration, a) sensor, b) voltage amplifier..... 25

Figure 22 - End-effector perception architecture: slip identification, pose estimation through pressure images and robot goal adjustment 26

Figure 23 - Velostat Pressure Matrix (VPM) prototype 27

Figure 24 - Circuit diagram of Velostat Pressure Matrix (VPM)..... 27

Figure 25 - VPM pressure readings and slipping vector estimation..... 28

Figure 26 - 15x15 VPM configuration 29

Figure 27 - Generation of simulated pressure profile from CAD files..... 29

Figure 28 - Plane wing segment assembly configuration and “skin” part to be positioned 30

Figure 29 - Assembly line and stationary fixture with the skin part positioned for operations..... 31

Figure 30 - Layout of the assembly cell 31

Figure 31 - Detailed design of the developed solution..... 32

Figure 32 - Vacuum gripper 33

Figure 33 - Vacuum gripper 33

Figure 34 - Rotary and linear actuators included in the part positioning solution 34

Figure 35 - Force sensors integrated in the stationary fixture 35

Figure 36 - Software modules of the mechatronic coupling controller 35

Figure 37 - Vision system for part holes identification..... 36

Figure 38 - Gazebo simulation to check sensor candidates..... 37

Figure 39 - Pattern of the Mid 70 3D laser under different configurations 37

Figure 40 - Livox 3D sensors located on the trolley’s crane..... 38

Figure 41 - Telemeter for trolley position 38

Figure 42 – Representation of the PC installed on crane’s cabinet 39

Figure 43 – Schematic representation of the software modules for smart crane..... 40

Figure 44 - Merged point cloud from sensors 41

Figure 43 - Occupancy map 41

Figure 46 - Workflow of anticollision system..... 42

Figure 47 - Screenshot of anticollision system..... 42

Table of tables

Table 1 - Technical Specifications of COMAU Agile1500	10
Table 2 - COMAU Racer5 Cobot technical specifications	14
Table 3 - Specifications of the proximity sensors to install in the gripper	19

1 Introduction

WP2 is one of the technical work packages of the MASTERLY project, together with WP3, WP4, WP5, and WP6. This work package is named “MASTERLY multi-disciplinary smart mechatronics for intelligent workpiece handling” and aims to design a versatile mechatronics system incorporating navigation skills and capable of grabbing, holding and manipulating objects of different sizes and shapes, hence meeting the requirements identified in WP1. The results developed in the current WP build on four key pillars: cooperation between AGVs and robotic arms for autonomous task execution, development of versatile grippers for a wide range of tasks, integration of sensors for precise object identification, and development of intelligent stationary fixtures with integrated sensors and actuators. In this deliverable, we present the results achieved during the first 18 months of work under WP2. It includes a detailed description of the development of initial prototypes for the targeted smart mechatronics.

Although a few of the previous objectives were specifically tailored to fit certain pilot cases of the project, it has always been essential to identify and develop a common solution capable of addressing all pilot cases comprehensively. The three pilot cases involve the assembly of electrical cabinets, the packaging of orders, and the production of large composite panels, in collaboration with Kleemann, Decathlon, and Aernnova, respectively. The objects to be manipulated exhibit a wide range of physical and mechanical features, such as rigidity, size, and texture. Further details about the pilot cases, requirements, and objectives are reported in D1.1. In this fragmented scenario, IIT identified a technological solution to meet the requirements of the three pilot cases. Specifically, IIT developed a two-finger parallel gripper with two degrees of freedom (DOF) and equipped with suction cups. The fingers open and close as a parallel jaw and can also pivot around the joint to grasp large objects. Additionally, suction cups are installed on the fingertips and the inner sides of the fingers: the former can pick up small objects by closing the fingers, while the latter can grab large objects and prevent the deformation of soft/flexible objects from causing grasping loss. Furthermore, the fingers can open to a spread of 180 degrees, allowing them to adhere to large surfaces and ensure a secure grasp. A schematic representation of such a robotic solution is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Schematic representation of the flexibility of the design the smart gripper, suitable for the three different pilot cases with the opportune tailored adjustments. The fingers of the gripper can move linearly (left column), rotate to grab large objects (central column), and spread open at 180 degrees to grab large flat surfaces (right column).

Conversely, a detailed representation of the functional design of the grippers, modelling the mechanical components and the kinematics behaviour is reported in the right-hand side of Figure 2, which highlights the connection between the final designs and the unique general robotics solution.

Figure 2 – Representation of the functional design of the smart gripper, including mechanical components and modelling the kinematics behaviour.

After a thorough examination of the industrial plants and production processes for the three pilot cases, it was possible to identify a macrocategory of object features for each use case. Specifically, the majority of products to handle are small flexible items for Decathlon, small rigid items for Kleeman, and large rigid items for Aernnova. Consequently, the common solution presented in this section had to be tailored on the requirements of each specific use case. Detailed descriptions of the smart mechatronics devices designed and developed for the Decathlon, Kleeman, and Aernnova use cases are reported in Section 2.3, Section 2.4, and Section 2.5, respectively.

2 Task-driven progress

In this section it is reported the output of the activities carried out in the last period of the project with a special focus on each specific task that compose WP2. Each subsection is dedicated to the description of the solutions adopted from both hardware and software point of view, according to the requirements defined in D1.1 for the several pilot cases. The structure of the section matches the same structure of the WP2 in terms of tasks to have an easy and quick understanding and correlation of the activities.

2.1 Task 2.1: AGVs for storage, retrieval and conveying of parts

The novel mobile platform manufactured by Comau would be based on the integration of two COMAU stand-alone robotic resources: the Agile 1500 AGV and the Racer5 Cobot (Figure 3). The adoption of such integrated platform will enable augmented flexibility in the production line as well as a high rate of reconfigurability of the platform in a complete collaborative and open environment.

Figure 3 - COMAU integrated mobile platform

The platform is equipped with two independent batteries for the electricity supply of the AGV and the robotic arm separately. For the first prototype, the two batteries are also charged separately and independently, using a custom charger structure with two sets of charging contacts. The battery, controller, inverter and internal cables of the robotic arm are placed inside the enclosure mounted on top of the AGV, which works as a base for the robotic arm itself. This structure is also used to provide the Racer5 Cobot with the different tools and racks which are required for different tasks execution. The stability of the platform during an emergency stop of the robotic arm is guaranteed by accurate studies and simulations of the dynamic behaviour of the platform, to ensure the highest levels of safety for the people and the surroundings.

Figure 4 describes the architecture of the safety system (in yellow) and its connection with the other elements of the AGV. In particular, the SICK safe PLC is connected to the two SICK S300 laser scanners via EFI, and to the Emergency stop, reset and mode switch buttons via safe I/Os. The safe PLC is also connected to the Kollmorgen CVC600 CPU, to the Drives and to the BMS via the CANopen protocol. The two laser scanners are also connected to the CPU to send scan data for navigation.

Figure 4 - Schematic representation of the safety architecture scheme of the Agile1500

2.1.1 Hardware modules

The selected moving platform is an AGV introduced by COMAU in order to increase its offer to customers. The vehicle differential drive architecture enables good stability and manoeuvrability (Figure 5 and Figure 6). It is capable of transporting up to 1500kg of payload and can withstand a maximum towing force of 2100N.

Figure 5 - COMAU Agile1500

Figure 6 - COMAU Agile1500 external dimensions

The AGV is capable of independently, accurately and safely finding the path to follow without colliding with people, machines or other AGVs. The available navigation modes are the following:

Natural navigation (standard)

Suitable for small or medium-sized environments where there are several reference points. It does not require any special integration into the operating environment.

Reflector navigation (standard)

Suitable for small, medium or large environments. The reflectors need to be installed in the facility. For the reflectors to work properly, it is necessary to map them using appropriate equipment.

Multi navigation: (Natural navigation + Magnetic navigation)

Suitable for environments of small, medium or large size and dynamic environments where it is not possible to use a sufficient number of fixed reference points. It is possible to use different navigation modes in more sections depending on the options provided and depending on the type of section in which it is located. Further technical details are provided in Table 1.

Table 1 - Technical Specifications of COMAU Agile1500

General data	Agile1500 (VCRGR-0000117780)
Mass	280kg
Noise	74dB max
Navigation modes	Natural, Reflector and Multi (Natural + Magnets)
IP protection degree	IP20

General data	Agile1500 (VCRGR-0000117780)
Type of power supply	Autonomous, Lithium batteries
Nominal voltage	25.6Vdc
Nominal capacity	138Ah
Battery charger voltage	28V
Battery power in standby	75W
Autonomy	4 hours at full load - 6 hours without load
Maximum speed (in a straight line)	Forward 1700mm/s Backward 1000mm/s
Minimum speed (continuous motion)	40mm/s
Maximum acceleration	400mm/s ² up to 1500
	380mm/s ² up to 1700
Maximum deceleration (cat. 1)	1500mm/s ²
Maximum torque in acceleration of each drive wheel	150Nm
Nominal traction torque in acceleration of each drive wheel	75Nm
Nominal traction power of the vehicle	2.1kW
Repeatability	±10mm
Antenna transmission frequency	2.4GHz
Relative humidity	5% to 95% without condensate
Maximum temperature gradient	1,5°C/min
Maximum transportable load	1500kg
Maximum towing force that can be applied for short periods	2100N
Maximum towing force that can be applied continuously	910N
Maximum distance of laser protected zone	3m resolution 70mm
Maximum distance of laser warning zone	8m resolution 70mm
Operating environment temperature	From 0°C to 45°C

General data	Agile1500 (VCRGR-0000117780)
Maximum floor slope	1%
Maximum flatness permitted	$\pm 2\text{mm/m}^2$
Maximum altitude of use	1000m above sea level

2.2 Task 2.2: Cooperating robots

The solution involves the application of cooperating robots in a Decathlon scenario, where both operators and robots work on the same conveyor belt (Figure 7). The main focus of the pilot consists in automating the products picking during the preparation of orders for shops and e-commerce, through the implementation of robotic platforms that can guarantee the required flexibility to handle multiple different products. The description of the overall process including requirements and specifications is reported in D1.1.

Figure 7 - Decathlon pilot case

2.2.1 Hardware modules

COMAU Racer5 Cobot (Figure 8) is a small robotic arm with a payload of 5kg that guarantees a reach of 0.8m and an accuracy of 0.03mm. It is able to switch from collaborative to non-collaborative speed during operation through the use of a laser scanner or barrier. It provides hand guidance for moving and teaching, and it is equipped with LEDs that produce information on the status of the robot (high speed mode / collaborative mode / collision with human / system alarm). Its collision detection is certified PL d Cat. 3 by TÜV Süd. The robot also is equipped with an RJ45 Ethernet connector and 2 Digital Inputs + 2 Digital Outputs on the wrist.

The workspace of the robot is visualized in Figure 9, while the technical details are listed in Table 2.

Figure 8 - COMAU Racer5 Cobot

Figure 9 - COMAU Racer5 Cobot workspace section

Table 2 - COMAU Racer5 Cobot technical specifications

VERSION		Racer-5-0.80 COBOT
Structure / No. of axes		Anthropomorphic / 6 axes
Maximum wrist load		5kg
Nominal wrist load		1kg
Axis 4 torque		8.83Nm
Axis 5 torque		8.83Nm
Axis 6 torque		4.91Nm
Admissible inertia on axis 4		0,42kg x m ²
Admissible inertia on axis 5		0,42kg x m ²
Admissible inertia on axis 6		0,18kg x m ²
Stroke (Speed)	Axis 1	+/- 169° (360°/s)
	Axis 2	-64° / +114° (300°/s)
	Axis 3	-150° / +60° (330°/s)
	Axis 4	+/- 200° (500°/s)
	Axis 5	- 105° / +100° (500°/s)
	Axis 6	+/- 2700° (800°/s)
Max horizontal reach		809mm
Repeatability		+/- 0.03mm
Robot weight		34kg
Features of the tool coupling Robot wrist		ISO 9409 - 1 - A 25
Motors		AC Brushless
Position measurement system		Encoder
Protection degree		IP54
Mounting position		Floor / Inverted / Angle / Wall
Operating environment temperature		from 5°C to +40°C
Storage temperature		from -10°C to +55°C

VERSION	Racer-5-0.80 COBOT
Relative humidity	5% to 95% without condensate
Maximum temperature gradient	1.5°C/min

2.2.2 Software modules

The Comau-ROS2 library repository contains all the required ROS2 packages to work with Comau robots through ROS. The package was tested under ROS2 Humble on Ubuntu 22.04 LTS. The library is based to TCP/IP communication between the ROS2 module running on an external PC and the PDL module running on the cabinet IPC; it is also possible to use the library in virtual mode. In this case, the user only needs a laptop where both Windows and Linux run respectively needed to support RoboShop software tool (COMAU virtual environment) and ROS2. The overall architecture of the ROS2 module is reported in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Schematic representation of the COMAU ROS driver architecture

For both the AGILE 1500 and RACER 5L cobot, the ROS network will continuously publish topics as messages, services, and actions. This real-time communication ensures that all system components are updated with the latest information, facilitating effective monitoring of the robot's operations. The specific implementation of this module is reported on D5.1 with the detailed list of all the types of messages, services and actions used and the overall architecture developed.

2.3 Task 2.3: Dexterous grippers for handling of flexible materials

Using robotic grippers to handle flexible materials presents several challenges due to their tendency to deform when forces are applied, making it difficult for traditional rigid grippers to grasp them without causing damage. Additionally, variations in the texture and size of soft objects necessitate adaptable and versatile gripping mechanisms, which can be complex to design and implement. These difficulties highlight the need for innovative solutions in robotic gripper technology to ensure safe and effective manipulation of soft materials.

IIT worked on designing a mechatronic device tailored to the products in the Decathlon warehouse, based on the common solution presented in Section 3. Most of these objects consist of soft, flexible materials that can undergo elastic deformation and/or are made of various materials, making conventional grasping strategies ineffective. However, a small portion of the identified objects are rigid or packed in rigid materials. Consequently, the designed gripper must be capable of handling both rigid and soft objects.

The idea originated from a study on the properties of a subset of products in the Decathlon warehouse. In order to evaluate the response of the flexible products to conventional grippers, IIT organized a series of test sessions in the warehouse with two and three fingers gripper, and with vacuum gripper, varying the number of suction caps, their width (*i.e.*, the suction power), and the technology used: vacuum or Venturi. A gallery of the grippers used for the tests is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 - Representation of the conventional grippers tested at the Decathlon warehouse during the test sessions. The performance of a suction gripper was evaluated, by varying the number of suction caps, their width and the technology (*i.e.*, vacuum or Venturi). Moreover, a two- and a three-finger grippers were tested.

IIT tested the grasping performance of the grippers on a few dozen products, characterized by a wide variety of features, such as hanging holes, bags or boxes in the packaging, potential for entanglement in the box, rigidity, foldability, presence of wrapping elastic bands, and composition of different materials (Figure 12).

Figure 12 - A sample of the tests conducted at the Decathlon warehouse. Different grippers (by rows) are placed in position over the targeted product, once the grasp is secured, the products are lifted and manipulated to test the grasping stability and explore potential issues.

During the test sessions, the grippers were applied in different locations of the products, not only in the center of mass, or over specific features that could contribute to the success of the grasp, such as hooks, holes or bands. As a result, IIT recorded several issues that occurred during grasping. Specifically, some bags popped when the suction caps were applied, some objects were too heavy, and some identified grasping features were damaged during manipulation.

The subset of tested products includes yoga pants and mats, drinking bottles, backpacks, shoes, camping cutlery, bike locks, sleeping bags, and wind jackets, among others. This selection was made to study as many different features as possible. A sample of test products is depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13 - A sample of the test products selected to evaluate the performance of conventional grasping strategies.

The features analyzed during the test phase, along with the results, grasping performance, and highlights of the grasping strategies, were recorded and saved in a database. This database was initially preprocessed and adapted to fit the requirements of a multilayer perceptron (MLP), a popular neural network architecture widely used for classification problems. In particular, the performance results were expressed as a percentage, any source of bias was compensated, all the values were normalized and the text data were categorized. In this scenario, an MLP was trained to predict the type of gripper recommended for grabbing a specific product based solely on its features. The extracted and observed features are reported in the following list:

- Box dimensions
- Number of items per box
- Product dimension
- Maximum product dimension
- Packed products
- Presence of knots
- Presence of holes
- Presence of cardboards
- Rigidity
- Foldability
- Potential for entanglement
- Presence of bag
- Materials
- Need for slow manipulation
- Picking area

One significant result that emerged from the database analysis was the low efficiency of the three-finger gripper. It turned out to be applicable to fewer objects and performed worse compared to the two-finger version.

2.3.1 Hardware modules

IIT focused on a robotic solution that could account for both grasping technologies, initially developing a finger-changing tool. However, this solution proved to be too expensive and time-consuming, failing to meet the Masterly requirements. Therefore, integrating both grasping techniques emerged as a viable solution to successfully grasp the vast majority of products at the Decathlon premises. The gripper was designed as a two-finger parallel gripper with two degrees of freedom (DOF), enabling the opening and closing of the fingers and rotation to grab large objects. Moreover, each finger was equipped with two suction caps, one on the fingertip and one on the internal side, to pick small objects using suction and enhance grasping through a combination of force and suction, respectively.

The suction caps for the fingers were selected from those tested at the Decathlon warehouse. The choice was driven by the need to balance several factors: keeping the fingers as thin as possible to pick very small products, maintaining a low weight, and avoiding unintentional damage to products in the box, while still ensuring high grasping performance. Therefore, the small black vacuum cups were identified as the optimal trade-off.

In order to drive the lateral movement of the fingers and the rotation for opening and closing, three linear actuators were selected and installed in the gripper. The selected models are compact, high-performance motorised linear actuators with a 100mm stroke, 12V DC power, and 800N max force, featuring IP54 protection (Figure 14).

Figure 14 - Representation of the selected linear actuators. Image downloaded from the manufacturer website.

Moreover, the gripper was equipped with proximity sensors to prevent the gripper from touching and damaging untargetted products and to implement slip detection. Further details on the software are described in Section 2.3.2. In order to keep the design of the fingers thin, two slim sensors were installed in the fingers, next to the suction caps, with a detection range up to 6mm. Moreover, a bulky sensor with a detection range up to 250mm was installed in the palm of the gripper. A representation of the selected sensors is depicted in Figure 15, while their features are reported in Table 3.

Figure 15 - Representation of the selected linear actuators. a) The slim model to install in the fingers. b) The bulky sensor to install in the palm of the gripper.

Table 3 - Specifications of the proximity sensors to install in the gripper

Feature	Finger sensor	Palm sensor
Sensing Range	6mm	20mm to 250mm
Unstable area	< 1.2mm	< 20mm

Feature	Finger sensor	Palm sensor
Operating voltage	1V to 30V	24V
Dimensions	6.5mm x 6.5mm x 31.5mm	31mm x 12mm x 23mm
Mass	NA	10g

The final design of the first prototype of the gripper is represented in Figure 16.

Figure 16 - Representation of the final design of the first prototype of the gripper designed to meet the requirements of the Decathlon pilot case.

2.3.2 Software modules

The gripper was equipped with proximity sensors as detailed in Section 2.3.1. The sensors to install in the fingers were selected with a low sensing range, prioritizing the reduced volume. These devices will flag the presence of untargeted objects too close to the gripper during the grasping phase. In the case objects are detected, the robotic arm will stop and transmit to the planning algorithm the need to modify the target object or compute a different grasping trajectory. This approach enhances the performance of grasping the targeted object while minimizing or avoiding collisions that could damage surrounding objects in the box.

Conversely, the additional sensor installed in the palm was selected for its high sensing range. This feature enables the detection of objects grasped by the suction caps at the end of the fingers or those placed further away. Moreover, the continuous acquisition of information enables the detection of variation of grasping position. As a consequence, this result is directly translated into slip detection or, worst case scenario, loss detection. In the case slip or loss is detected, the gripper can adjust the position of the fingers to increase applied force, or it can be applied to a different highly stable grasping point.

2.4 Task 2.4: Grippers to handle rigid materials of variable size, shape and weight

The abilities of robotic agents rely on the capabilities of the deployed end-effectors. Developing end-effectors to handle objects of variant size, shape, weight, texture, etc. presents significant challenges. The main difficulty lies on developing a cost-effective and cognition-empowered device that can securely and accurately grasp, handle and manipulate diverse objects without any excess tool modifications, manual adjustments. The activities of this task are the result of a study performed by LMS and TF-CC in an effort to deliver a robotic end-effector able to address the functional requirements and the manufacturing challenges of electrical cabinet assembly, as those are expressed by KLEEMANN, documented in deliverables D1.1 and D1.2.

2.4.1 Hardware modules

Despite drawing inspiration by the control panel boards manufacturing industry, effort on the design of the end-effector has been oriented towards providing a holistic solution in automating processes of bin-picking and assembly operations, and act as a reference for engineers facing similar challenges.

2.4.1.1 Methodology

The main objective was to deliver a solution that without time costly tool changes can perform the following tasks: a) sort out objects from tight spaces, b) in-hand manipulation of objects, c) assemble electrical components. Robotic solutions that can handle the aforementioned tasks all at once are limited, due to the diversity of components dimensions, shape, and weight, amongst many features. In order to design a device capable of handling as many electrical components as possible, the implementation of a combined solution through vacuum and parallel grasping technologies is considered requisite. Vacuum is suitable in grasping objects from occluded scenes, where there is limited accessibility for multi-sided grasping. Moreover, parallel finger grippers are more suitable in assembly operations, where high accuracy is needed. Figure 17 describes the approach of sorting out objects through vacuum, in-hand manipulate the object through appropriate degrees of freedom and clamp it through a parallel finger mechanism to be assembled. This methodology combines the benefits of each grasping technology in a seamless and efficient sequential manner.

Figure 17 - Handling approach on complete pick and place operation

2.4.1.2 Implementation

Inspired by the functional requirements in the electrical panel assembly process, the design integrates four sub-mechanisms in one device that can perform a complete sequence of automated picking and placing tasks at a low cost (Figure 18):

1. Lateral motion adjustment of suction cups: the mechanism consists of two different size suction cups, that can laterally move with respect to one another. One suction cup remains static, while the other is driven by two linear brushless motors. The lateral adjustment is designed for better grasping small to medium sized components, by adapting to the free surface.
2. Downwards motion of suction cups: apart from the lateral adjustment, both suction cups can extend/retract downwards, with the utilization of two double acting pneumatic cylinders mounted. This downwards motion creates a much-needed clearance around the suction cups from the rest of the device, allowing for collision-free access inside tight containers.
3. Rotation of suction cups: a 90-degree rotation has been introduced in both suction cups as well. The motivation behind such implementation comes from the industrial challenge of automatically grasp randomly placed objects in difficult positions (like facing the walls of a container). While space inside the containers is limited and full rotation of the gripper inside is difficult to achieve proper suction orientation, the rotation of the suction cups comes to solve this issue.
4. Parallel clamp gripper: an independent double-acting, linearly-guided pneumatic cylinder actuates two flanges that clamp objects in between. The clamp gripper works as a traditional clamping mechanism, picking and placing objects that has access to, but can also be fed with electrical components through the aforementioned mechanisms of the suction cups. This allows for direct bin picking and assembling tasks without regrasping actions in between.

Figure 18 - Device mechanisms: 1) Lateral motion adjustment of suction cups, 2) Downwards motion of suction cups, 3) Rotation of suction cups, 4) Parallel clamp gripper.

The device shown in Figure 18 has a minimum bounding box of 240mm(L)x200mm(W)x220mm(H) when all sub-mechanisms are fully retracted. Two linear brushless motors control the lateral distance between the two suction cups, achieving 30mm minimum separation and 77mm at maximum range. The proposed design allows for an easy expansion of the linear guides used by the motors, allowing for manipulation of small to medium sized objects. Regarding the expansion/retraction mechanism, the suction cups have the ability to extend up to 75mm from their initial position. As for the clamping mechanism, it can handle objects with approx. maximum width of 70mm. Overall, the vacuum gripper, including both suction cups, has a carrying capacity of 0.5kg at 0,6bar of vacuum pressure. Adjusting the vacuum pressure enables the linearly growing handling forces.

Figure 19 showcases the sequence of motions that allow for an effortless bin-pick and secure to be assembled operation. Considering that multiple components are randomly placed inside a container, the end-effector extends the two suction cups to create a required clearance around and enter the container. After successful suction, the component is rotated 90-degrees to be aligned with the open jaws of the clamping gripper. Retraction of the suction cups upwards puts the object in proper position inside the clamp jaws. The actuation of the clamp gripper pneumatic cylinder secures the component in a predetermined position. The component is then secured and ready to be transported and assembled to the electrical cabinet.

Figure 19 - Kinematics of mechatronic end-effector for small- to medium-sized components: a) downwards extension of suction cups, b) 90-degree rotation of suction cups, and c) Upwards retraction of suction cups, d) Parallel clamp.

2.4.2 Software modules

LMS together with TF-CC are working on enhancing the cognition capabilities of the robot throughout grasping, towards increasing robot's precision and adaptability to dynamically changing constraints. Considering a successful grasp, equally important is whether the component is still in proper orientation and pose or has deviated from the initial one. The development of algorithms for grasp detection, slip and total failure are critical on allowing the robotic system to take autonomously respective actions based on the captured sensing inputs.

2.4.2.1 Methodology

Research community has worked upon multiple approaches on how to increase the end-effectors' perception capabilities. These approaches can include AI-enhanced, vision-based systems or other sensorial that allow for increased cognition during operation. While vision-based algorithms can be more accurate, they are more complex to develop and deploy on the fly. In this regard, and for this specific application of the end-effector, it was considered that the development of sensors, based on tactile capabilities, can offer quicker information on the handling of objects.

Two methods were considered the most appropriate for collecting information from the end-effector device. Both methods have the goal of collecting data related to the presence or absence of an object that is grasped, the slipping of the object when it is grasped, as well as the failure of grasping in unsuccessful scenarios. The first method utilizes arrays of conductive material separated with a piezoresistive foil called Velostat, while the second method employs multiple tactile sensors arranged in a matrix.

1st approach – Piezoresistive matrix perception

The detection of the presence or absence of an object can easily be monitored through the readings of the sensor. The detection of grasp stability, though, and in consequence the slip detection, relies on monitoring and comparing the differences between recorded forces at consecutive time intervals. A stable grasp results in no covariance between forces, throughout time. In order to test this approach, a thin pressure mat is constructed. The principle is based on the change of resistance of the Velostat foil, when pressure is applied on top. When implementing two electrodes sandwiching the foil from both sides, and applying current to pass through, a voltage difference is measured. This voltage difference, when calibrated properly can provide good evidence of the clamping force, and more easily provide evidence of grasping, slipping and total failure of grasp.

The electrodes that are used in this case are multiple arrays of copper tape. The sensor is formed by two layers of copper wires arranged in a grid pattern, the top layer set parallel to x-axis, while the bottom set perpendicular to y-axis. Insulation films were applied to both outer surfaces, to prevent short-circuits and avoid false readings. A schematic representation of the pressure mat is seen in Figure 20.

Figure 20 - Velostat piezoresistive material configuration

2nd approach – Tactile sensing

The second approach that will be developed will utilize multiple small tactile sensors, arranged in a grid pattern, similarly to the first approach. These sensors, work independently and measure pressure,

allowing for an accurate mapping of the forces around the mat's surface. In practice, each sensor converts a mechanical stimulus into an electrical signal, to be fed into a microcontroller unit and process it to generate data. As seen in Figure 21, each tactile sensor requires a sensor amplifier to enhance the output current. As a consequence, the data are readable by the controller and can be processed.

Figure 21 - Tactile sensing configuration, a) sensor, b) voltage amplifier

Perception architecture of end-effector

The slip detection module enables the processing the readings from the pressure mat. This module is developed in principle to identify grasp, estimate whether significant slipping is occurring on the grasped part, or total loss of the part. The core of the slip detection relies on comparing the current pressure values with the previous readings. This comparison helps identify regions of the sensor grid where rapid changes in pressure occur, which may indicate a slip event.

For each sensor in the grid, the script calculates the change between the current and previous readings. This is done by subtracting the previous value from the current value. A threshold value is set to determine whether the rate of change is significant enough to be considered a slip. If the absolute value of the rate of change exceeds this threshold, it is flagged as a potential slip. Among all the sensors that exceed the slip threshold, the script identifies the one with the highest absolute rate of change. This sensor is considered the most likely source of the slip. Once a slip is detected, the script calculates the gradient of the pressure data using central differences. The slip direction takes the form of a vector that its first component is the gradient of the pressure readings in the x-axis and its second component is the gradient of the pressure readings in the y axis. In order to ensure the direction vector has a consistent magnitude, it is normalized. Normalization involves dividing the vector by its magnitude (if the magnitude is not zero). The detected direction is further smoothed using an exponential moving average filter to reduce noise and provide a more stable direction vector.

The slipping can be quantitatively estimated by calculating the translational offset of the part centroid, together with the rotational offset of the object. In order to do so, a second module needs to be developed that takes into account the object's pressure image, from the sensor, and fuse the data to the object CAD data. This matching can occur with different approaches. Either a least square approach can be followed to estimate a minimum sum of squared distances, through a regression analysis or a CNN can be trained to fuse pressure image data with the CAD layer data.

While simple in conception, the training of such a CNN requires careful consideration of the data collections and the preprocessing of the feeding data to create an accurate and robust model that can export an accurate pose of the grasped object.

Having developed the slip detection module together with the pose estimation module based on the pressure images, a pose offset can be estimated when slipping is detected. The offset can occur, for example, if an external force is applied to the object during wrong assembly. In the case of KLEEMANN, this is possible when robot assembles electrical components on top of the DIN rails. Accurately identifying this offset is critical in correcting robot's goal position and sending a new goal for an accurate assembly of parts. The assembly of the electrical parts occurs through a force/torque control method, which can trigger the slip detection module when the desired assembly solution cannot be achieved.

A schematic representation of the perception architecture is depicted in Figure 22.

Figure 22 - End-effector perception architecture: slip identification, pose estimation through pressure images and robot goal adjustment

2.4.2.2 Implementation

The initial step involves constructing the sensor, which is housed on top of a PLA 3D-printed frame. The sensor comprises of five layers:

1. Base Layer: a leather patch serves as the foundation.
2. First Copper Layer: a thin PC plastic film with six 5mm copper tape rows adhered to it is placed above the leather patch.
3. Velostat Layer: a thin film of velostat fabric that completely covers the copper rows on the first plastic film.
4. Second Copper Layer: an additional thin PC plastic film with six 5mm copper tape rows, oriented at a 90-degree angle to the rows on the first plastic film, is placed on top of the velostat layer.
5. Top Layer: a second leather patch covers the entire assembly.

The copper rows in both plastic film layers must be fully covered by the Velostat layer and in complete contact with it. This configuration creates a 36-pixel pressure matrix. The plastic films with copper rows are glued to the respective leather patches, and the leather patches are sewn together to encapsulate the

other layers securely. The construction is consisted of simple steps, though it requires precision during assembly, to avoid structural defects that will diverge the readings. The prototype sensor is depicted in Figure 23.

Figure 23 - Velostat Pressure Matrix (VPM) prototype

Circuit diagram of VPM

The circuit diagram that has been developed is seen in Figure 24. Two multiplexers are used to combine the analog input signals coming from the voltage difference, into one single output signal that can be read by the microcontroller. The sensor operates by applying a voltage to the bottom layer and measuring the voltage from the top layer. Due to the piezoresistive nature of the Velostat fabric, its resistance increases when pressure is applied, resulting in a decrease in the voltage read from the top layer. These voltage changes can be quantified and scaled to correlate with specific pressure values, allowing for precise pressure measurements.

Figure 24 - Circuit diagram of Velostat Pressure Matrix (VPM)

Estimating and visualizing the slip vector

The detection of object offset, particularly in the context of slip estimation, relies on monitoring the temporal evolution of pressure measured through the developed sensing grid. This sensing grid continuously collect real-time data. In the case an object is in contact with the sensor and, consequently, applies some external force, it generates an orthogonal pressure measured by the sensors. Continuously monitoring this pressure allows for the estimation of active sliding conditions. The slip vector computation involves:

- Collecting raw pressure data;
- Measuring the pressure changes in each pixel of the sensor, if a slip threshold is exceeded, we calculate the pressure gradient in X and Y directions to generate the slip indices;
- Compute slip indices along X and Y directions and combine them to generate the slip vector.

The smoothed direction vector is then used to visualize the slip direction on a separate 2D plot. In the case a slip is detected, the vector is updated and displayed. Figure 25 shows the real-time data that are captured when an external force is applied on top of the sensor. The module detects pressure anomalies and estimates the direction of the slipping, taking into account the pressure gradient of all grid cells and identifies the largest differences in pressure.

Figure 25 - VPM pressure readings and slipping vector estimation

By applying appropriate thresholds on the magnitude of change, slipping can be quantified and detected in real time. This slip can affect the assembly operations and influence the accuracy of the operations. Hence, based on the perception architecture that was described earlier, this module is utilized as the triggering point on identifying the new pose of the object and, accordingly, send a new goal offset to the robot. Sending a new robot goal means that one does not compromise the assembly accuracy if unexpected slipping occurs, on the contrary robot can autonomously adapt and stay operational.

15x15 Velostat Pressure Matrix

In addition to the 6x6 pressure matrix, a larger configuration was developed to evaluate the consistency of the hardware readings and to facilitate experiments with larger objects. The new configuration has a 15x15 grid and will assist on training the CNN to a more extensive dataset, in various objects and pose configurations (Figure 26).

Figure 26 - 15x15 VPM configuration

Pressure profile

Progress has already been made in developing a module to generate the simulated pressure profile of an object from its CAD file. This is achieved by creating a triangular mesh of the object using its CAD file and calculating the number of triangle vertices located within each pixel of the sensor for the side of the object that touches the sensor (Figure 27). Future efforts will focus on calculating the complete set of possible pressure profiles for an object, encompassing all potential translations and rotations on the sensor.

Figure 27 - Generation of simulated pressure profile from CAD files

2.5 Task 2.5: Intelligent stationary fixtures

2.5.1 Hardware modules

In this task the objective is to develop a solution for the automatic placement of large, flat parts into position in an assembly fixture of the aeronautics use case. In the following image, a typical plane wing segment is shown. It is composed of an inner metallic structure and a flat part manufactured in composite material commonly called “skin” that covers the structure. This part must be placed into position with high accuracy so, afterward, different types of processes like riveting and fixing additional components can be performed.

Figure 28 - Plane wing segment assembly configuration and “skin” part to be positioned

Currently, the positioning of the skin is done in assembly cells by a fully manual procedure. Three operators work in unison, one of them controlling the crane and the other two aiding in positioning the skin into place and putting the fixing pins to hold the part in place. In Figure 29 such an assembly line is shown. In the second image the stationary fixture can be seen where the assembly of the skin is done.

Figure 29 - Assembly line and stationary fixture with the skin part positioned for operations

Implementation

Figure 30 - Layout of the assembly cell

Concerning the work carried out in this task, a detailed solution has been developed for the automatic positioning of the skin into place in the intelligent stationary fixture. This solution consists of a mechatronic gripper system that uses vacuum cups to hold the part, a vision system to identify the position and orientation of the part, and a series of actuators that will position the part into place in the fixture. Additionally, force sensors located in the stationary fixture will provide input signals of the assembly forces appearing during the procedure. In the following picture, a detailed 3D design of the developed system is shown. The system is composed of the stationary fixture (*i.e.* the fixture on the right-end side of the image) and in front of it there is second auxiliary fixture equipped with the suction cup gripper.

Figure 31 - Detailed design of the developed solution

In the image it can be seen how the part is held by the gripper by using six vacuum cups. The secondary fixture can move back around 1 meter to allow sufficient space for the part to be brought to the suction cups. For this operation, a second vision system in development will aid the operator by identifying the optimal grasping points in the part with vision technology and showing the optimal grasping points by

means of a projector that will project crosses into the part's surface, or maybe an augmented reality interface (to be defined).

Then, the carriage moves forward putting the part close to the stationary fixture. At that point, the main vision system consisting of one or several cameras will measure the current exact pose (*i.e.* position and orientation) of the part. This input will be used to command the actuators of the mechatronic gripping system.

The vacuum gripper used currently by Aernnova is a VacuMaster Basic 250 kg by Schmalz, as seen in the following figure.

Figure 32 - Vacuum gripper

The position of the vacuum cups will be defined as a reference position related to the local coordinate system of the skin part. Furthermore, a spherical joint will be added to the vacuum cup to allow the adaptation of the cup position to the surface normal of the skin.

Figure 33 - Vacuum gripper

The clamping force needed in the vacuum cups is related to the elastic recovery force of the skin, the geometrical difference between the resting position and the deformed position, and the stiffness of the skin. The skin is manufactured to closely match the final shape, although some deviations may occur during the production process. In the case the skin is picked with a deformation, it would generate a recovery force as the skin tends to recover its position. It is expected to be a low elastic force, so the vacuum cups must be able to support the gravity force plus the recovery forces.

Once the part is held by the vacuum cups, a series of actuators that provide movement along one rotary axis and three linear axes will precisely locate the part into position with an accuracy of 0.1mm. At that point, fixing pins can be put into place to immobilize the part in the stationary fixture for its further processing. In the following image a detail of the actuators used in the system solution is shown.

Figure 34 - Rotary and linear actuators included in the part positioning solution

During the positioning and clamping of the part in the stationary fixture, assembly reaction forces in the support pins will be monitored, mainly shear and bending load. A design for the sensorized pins has been developed by the integration of strain gauges. A first design that can perform shear load measurement has been implemented. This design includes two measurement sections (reduced section with squared shape). The bending load pin design is still under development. The information gathered by the force sensors integrated in the fixing pins will be checked to understand if the part is reaching the maximum stress threshold in compliance with the design to ensure its integrity and therefore ensure a longer life cycle during real performance. Moreover, the force will be correlated with geometrical data to study the relationship between both types of data. The analysis aims to evaluate different data sources to improve the assembly process sequence. Further information regarding this system is provided in deliverable D3.1, in the section “Force monitoring during the assembly of big aerospace components”. In Figure 35 a detail of the sensorized fixing pin is shown.

Figure 35 - Force sensors integrated in the stationary fixture

2.5.2 Software modules

In the following block diagram, the different software modules currently under development are shown.

Figure 36 - Software modules of the mechatronic coupling controller

As seen in the diagram, there exist two different vision systems involved in the general solution. The objective of the first one is to detect the part as brought by the smart crane and help the operator to position the part relative to the suction cups according to the optimal grasping position.

The second vision system will in turn calculate the pose of the part already grasped by vacuum and give the actuators the required commands, so they can place the part in its final position with the required accuracy. For this purpose, a single camera or a dual camera system will detect the reference holes in the images and calculate their centre. Consequently, the exact pose of the part (around 0.1mm accuracy) will be calculated.

Figure 37 - Vision system for part holes identification

2.6 Task 2.6: Smart cranes for autonomous transportation of large parts

Concerning the development of smart cranes for autonomous transportation of large parts, the following works have been completed:

- Definition of specifications and process constraints for the smart crane system.
- Mechanical and electrical design for enhancement of conventional cranes.
- Design and development of sensor-based solutions for 3D perception and safe automatic part handling.
- Design and development of swing control algorithm.

Consequently, the implementation of a Smart Crane with integrated sensors can be considered as completed for a GH crane. It includes the required hardware, together with the swing control algorithms. The drivers for ROS are ready for the sensors and the software control topics, messages and actions are defined and implemented for the interaction with the smart crane.

2.6.1 Hardware modules

The objective of this task is to improve the design and performance of conventional cranes by the implementation of sensing and smart functionalities, generation of collision-free trajectories and controlling the swinging of transported parts.

To provide environmental awareness to the crane, it was equipped with 3D laser sensors that provide a point cloud, from which a representation of the environment is obtained. The output of these sensors can be used for collision algorithms. In the selection phase of the 3D laser sensors, factors such as range, resolution, data acquisition frequency, coverage or angle of vision, among others, were estimated.

To solve and test several of these aspects a simulation was created, mainly to evaluate the ideal position and the number of sensors needed to cover the appropriate area to facilitate an anti-collision functionality. A screenshot of the simulation is shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38 - Gazebo simulation to check sensor candidates

Some candidate sensors were tested in the simulation. The result of this simulation showed Livox Mid70 sensors as suitable. These sensors have the advantage that in static situations, as they have a known random pattern, they allow a better definition of the environment than other 3D sensors. The following picture shows the Livox Mid70 3D sensor pattern under different configurations.

Figure 39 - Pattern of the Mid 70 3D laser under different configurations

The simulation also facilitated the suitable positioning of the sensors on the crane. The proper arrangement for these sensors consisted of two Livox sensors at both ends of the crane trolley. The following image shows the sensors located on the crane trolley.

Figure 40 - Livox 3D sensors located on the trolley's crane

Sensors were introduced on the crane to know its position at every moment. This helps the creation of a map of the plant for subsequent path planning. Figure 41 shows the telemeter for trolley position.

Figure 41 - Telemeter for trolley position

Finally, a TURCK B2N85H inclinometer was installed at the hoist system of the crane, the pulley-cable system that oversees the vertical movement of the load. This inclinometer provides accurate inclination measurement and the inclination rate of the load with respect to the cart, which is used to feed the closed loop anti-swing control.

The crane hardware was completed with a PC-based on-board system which oversees collecting sensor data, digitalizing the data in a map carrying out the computation for the collision avoidance system and a tiltmeter to feed the anti-swing system.

Figure 42 – Representation of the PC installed on crane’s cabinet

2.6.2 Software modules

The role of the smart crane software module in the aeronautics pilot case consists of ensuring an automatic and safe procedure to move the part from the transportation trolley to the mechatronic gripping system. This handling must avoid part deformation as well as unstable manipulation avoiding swing and collisions with objects or structures in the assembly area.

The automatic transportation will be successfully performed once the part is located within the assembly tooling area where the coarse positioning system will aid in holding the part with the vacuum cups of the mechatronic gripper. Even though the smart sensor will be dedicated to the crane operation, the 2D/3D data processing strategies will be as flexible as possible for transfer to other case studies.

A set of software functionalities has been developed to enable the automatic operation of the smart crane. The automatic part handling includes:

- Provide map and real time sensor data of the environment to path planning;
- Controlling the safe and precise displacement of the part from the initial to the final position;
- Monitoring the 3D environment of the workshop for the safe manipulation of the part as well as human interaction, providing to the operator with suitable warnings;
- Using the smart crane controller to automate part manipulation with stable and smooth movements by swing reduction;
- Ensuring that the part has been precisely located within the positioning range.

The following picture shows a block diagram of these functionalities:

Figure 43 – Schematic representation of the software modules for smart crane

An anti-swing control system has been included for safe and accurate manipulation of the load during transportation, as well as safety of the operators. A combination of the usage of open and closed loop anti-sway algorithms has been implemented for an optimized performance. Both open-loop and closed-loop approaches rely on a mathematical modelling of the crane system, based on a typical non-inverted pendulum model. One of the outcomes of the model is the dependency of dynamics of the system (i.e. its natural frequency of oscillation), to the rope length (i.e. the vertical distance from the cart to the load). Hence, both open and closed-loop algorithms are continuously fed by the instantaneous rope length, that is recorded by the PLC where this controller is implemented.

For the open loop approach, a dynamic notch filter is implemented, whose center frequency is adapted continuously according to rope length measurement, to match the natural frequency of the system. This way, velocity setpoints are filtered, avoiding excitation of the crane and, hence, providing smoother movements. However, due to modelling uncertainties, open-loop approach does not provide a perfect performance. In addition, open-loop approach does not react against external disturbances, like an operator assisting torsional rotation of a part, or initial elevation from the floor.

Hence, the open loop strategy has been complemented by a closed loop approach where the inclination of the load with respect to the cart is used to modify cart velocity and damp any oscillation. A simple proportional controller is applied to determine a velocity variation that is added to the nominal velocity of the cart coming from the setpoint generation (that can be filtered by the open loop anti-sway filter). A deep analysis of the closed loop system has been performed and an expression for the anti-sway control gain has been defined. This expression provides the gain value for a desired damping and depends on system parameters like rope length and load and cart mass. So, as for the open-loop algorithm, the controller continuously adapts the closed-loop gain to maintain the damping ratio even if the system is changed (rope length or load) and, this way, automatizes and optimizes the behavior.

The perception system is built based on the ROS operating system. It is the system in charge of taking the data of the crane position and the data coming from the sensors to have the environment digitized and thus being able to make decisions based on it. The ROS1 was chosen due to some drivers not being available at time of integration. Anyway, ROS bridge is available to communicate ROS1 and ROS2. Migration to ROS2 will be considered in the future.

For the position of the crane, data are directly taken from the telemeters by the PLC as a core part of the system. For the knowledge of the positions of the bridge, trolley and hook a ROS-OPCUA communication was implemented so that the perception system is aware of the position of the crane.

With respect to the capture of data from the sensors, first a calibration of the Livox sensors was performed, since it is necessary to know their relative position to properly merge the data from each of the point clouds of each sensor. To calculate the relative position, a point cloud matching algorithm called Normal Distributions Transform (NDT) was used. Once the calibration was carried out a ROS node for merging the point cloud was developed.

Figure 44 - Merged point cloud from sensors

With the merged point cloud, the environment perception system module can share data and build maps using position and sensor data using octomap server ROS node. This node was parameterized to optimize the resolution versus performance of the system. The following figure shows a 3D occupancy grid of the TEK facilities created by the octomap using the RVIZ ROS visualization tool.

Figure 45 - Occupancy map

The occupancy map provides workshop information, allowing route planning to know which space is free or occupied for planning. Obstacle detection or collision was developed. Figure 46 shows how it works.

Figure 46 - Workflow of anticollision system

The system works in the following way: the crane sensors supply the fused point cloud. This point cloud is cropped according to a given configuration. This allows points very far from the load to not being considered and this makes the calculation easier. After this, the crane parts of the point cloud are deleted. The resulting point cloud is fed to an octomap server. Using the flexible collision library, it calculates the minimum distance between the octomap and the parts of the crane, simplified in the configuration of the anti-collision system. If the system exceeds the preset minimum distance, the system sends an alert and it is also capable of showing the points in the RVIZ tool.

Figure 47 - Screenshot of anticollision system

Further information about ROS interfaces of modules is included in deliverable D5.1.

3 Conclusions

This deliverable has outlined the progress in developing the initial version of smart mechatronics devices within WP2. The work is focused on four main pillars: cooperation between AGVs and robotic arms for autonomous tasks, development of versatile grippers, integration of sensors for precise object identification, and creation of intelligent stationary fixtures with integrated sensors and actuators.

Comau presented their robotic platforms to enhance production line flexibility and reconfigurability, fostering a collaborative and open environment. Comau developed a novel mobile platform based on the integration of two COMAU stand-alone robotic resources: the Agile 1500 AGV and the Racer5 Cobot. Additionally, the Racer5 Cobot was identified as best candidate to tackle the Decathlon scenario, where operators and robots share the same conveyor belt. The focus is on automating product picking for orders, using robotic platforms to handle diverse products efficiently.

Furthermore, IIT developed a flexible modular gripping solution to meet the requirements of all three use cases. The general solution features a two-finger parallel gripper equipped with suction cups and characterized by 2 DOF. The fingers can open and close like a parallel jaw and pivot around the joint to grasp larger objects. This design served as the foundation for creating customized grippers tailored to the specific needs of each pilot case.

TEK completed the design of a mechatronic gripping system for the aeronautics use case. This system makes use of machine vision technology to accurately position the part to be processed into the intelligent stationary fixture, which in turn has got sensorized fixing pins to monitor assembly forces. Finally, a smart crane solution has been developed for the automatic and safe transportation of parts, by integrating sensors in a crane for 3D visualization of the environment, identifying and avoiding potential collisions, and reducing unwanted swing of large hanging parts with dedicated algorithms.

In conclusion, the progress detailed in this report represents significant advancements in smart mechatronics, paving the way for more efficient, adaptable, and collaborative robotic systems in industrial automation. Continued innovation and integration will further enhance these technologies, driving future developments in the field.